

BONDED REPAIRS IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES: A FINITE ELEMENT APPROACH

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SUMMARY: This paper reviews the use of the finite element method for the design and analysis of composite structural repairs. It compares a more traditional approach, based on that of Siener [7], with a 3D model and a new quasi-3D approach developed by Bair [8]. The predictive models are compared on the basis of displacement and adhesive tensile and shear stresses in repaired composite panels subjected to tensile loading. This work shows that the approaches are complementary, providing different insights into factors affecting the adhesive and the composite structure itself; both being important for the optimisation of repair joints. This study has also shown the need for an approach which provides an overall view of bonded repairs for composite structures.

KEYWORDS: adhesive bonded repairs, composite plates, finite element models

INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials in aircraft structures has become increasingly widespread as the need for improved aircraft performance and capabilities grows. Repair engineers increasingly find themselves having to design and analyse suitable repairs for in-service damage beyond the scope of experimentally derived structural repair manuals. Engineers advocate the development of analytical techniques for the design and evaluation of repair techniques. The popularity and widespread use of the finite element method as a numerical analysis tool in engineering make it a suitable candidate for such a task.

This paper reports the findings of the first phase of an on-going research project on the analysis of bonded repairs in composite structures using a PC-based finite element software..

MODELLING APPROACHES

Bonded repairs to composite structures share many features with adhesively bonded joints. As a result, the first approaches proposed for their study using the finite element method were based on models developed to analyse bonded joints. A good insight into the field of bonded repairs can be obtained from the extensive literature on adhesively bonded joints. Published works on bonded joints was extensively reviewed in 1982 by Matthews *et al.* in an excellent article with an emphasis on finite element analysis.

Given the growing popularity of the finite element method as an engineering tool, it is surprising that there is little literature directly concerned with the finite element modelling of composite repairs. This may be due to the fact that repair joints and structural joints share several common features. Thus given the amount of work devoted to understanding the latter, modelling specifically repair joints has not been pursued with the same endeavour. However repairing composite structures is a discipline in its own right. Hall *et al.*[2] have called specifically for an improvement in numerical analysis methods if more efficient repairs are to be designed; a view shared by Heslehurst [1] and also by Davis in his report on the development of a standard for composite repairs for the Royal Australian Air Force. Four modelling approaches have been proposed by Loss and Kedward, Jones *et al.*, Siener and Bair *et al.* which are milestones in the modelling of composite repairs.

This preliminary study has been carried out to evaluate different modelling approaches to composite repairs. In addition to full 3D models, two main alternatives have also been investigated following an extensive literature survey: Siener's model which is an extension of the traditional plane strain 2D model used for adhesive bonded joints and Bair's model which is a promising new approach. These models have been selected because of their suitability for PC-based finite element applications using commercial codes. The main objective of the present study was to explore the advantages and problems associated with each approach through a linear static analysis of a representative composite repair.

SIENER'S MODEL

The main feature of this model is the plane strain assumption. This reduces the analysis to a 2D problem. It has been used before to model bonded joints successfully and thus represents a natural first step into modelling repair joints. In his modelling of composite patch repairs, Siener [7] followed a method similar to Loss and Kedward [5] by working out equivalent orthotropic properties for the composite adherends and inputting them into the FE model.

Siener's investigation addressed the problem of reducing the repair joint overlap length in scarf repairs whilst providing sufficient strength restoration. It was shown that joint strength can be increased while reducing the overlap length by increasing the repair patch stiffness using different lamination sequences. However his attempt to accurately predict joint strength using this FE model was not very successful because it relies on equivalent orthotropic properties and material non-linearity was omitted.

From the laminate stacking sequence and material properties, effective properties are calculated using laminate analysis theory. These effective properties (Young's moduli, Poisson's ratios etc.) are then used in the material definition of the finite element model.

BAIR'S MODEL

The study by Bair *et al.* [8] is one of the very few published papers dedicated exclusively to the modelling of composite repairs. Unlike the previous model, a plane strain state is not assumed by cutting through the repair joint. Instead a quasi-3D model is built using 3D composite shell elements. The 3D composite shell elements include deformations due to membrane, bending, membrane-bending coupling and transverse shear effects and are made up of a number of perfectly bonded orthotropic layers. A repaired panel is therefore modelled

zone by zone with an appropriate number of dummy layers of very small stiffness is added to make up the maximum number of layers (Fig. 1); the number of layers staying the same across the whole model.

For the panel shown in Fig. 1, the dummy layers are indicated for zone A to illustrate this concept where a number of dummy layers are added to make up the same total number of layers as in the central part of the repair patch. The results from Bair's analysis have been compared to experimental data. Both data sets agree very well for strain measurements. Bair's model has its merits but there are doubts about whether features such as adhesive fillets and local geometric rounding can be represented using this approach. Furthermore, no indication has been given about material non-linearity. The main conclusion reached from this work was that the FEM could be used successfully on a day to day basis to design and analyse composite repairs for large area damage on a personal computer.

Fig. 1 Repaired panel configuration used by Bair et al.(8)

3D MODEL

This model employs 3D solid elements to represent both the adhesive and the composite adherends. For the former, simple isoparametric solid elements are used and for the latter composite solid elements. The aim is to obtain a full three dimensional representation of the stress state. The composite solid elements are also made of perfectly bonded orthotropic layers. Each adherend ply is modelled individually.

APPLICATION TO BONDED REPAIRS

These three approaches were used to model a scarf repair of a damaged composite plate. Siener's approach could be used to model an exact scarf, however, for the Bair approach the scarf joint was approximated by a five step lap joint. For the 3D model both types of repair were to be modelled. For reference purposes, undamaged and damaged plates were also modelled.

UNDAMAGED PLATE

The undamaged plate was a Hercules AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy composite with a stacking sequence of $[0_2 / \pm 45 / 90 / \pm 45 / 0_2]_s$. The laminate was 300 mm long, 25 mm wide and 2.5 mm thick, giving a layer thickness of 0.1389 mm for each lamina. Modelling the undamaged plate was straightforward. The three modelling approaches were used. The displacement and stress output from these models were used as references for the repaired plate as the aim in any repair scheme is to restore a damaged component to a fully functional state. 3D composite shell elements (NISA-NKTP 32) were used in Bair's approach, general shell elements (NKTP 20) for Siener's and both 3D solid elements (NKTP 4) and composite solid elements (NKTP 7) for the 3D model. Plane strain elements (NKTP 2) could have been used for Siener's model and hybrid solids (NKTP 9) for the adhesive in the 3D model. These hybrid solids are more suitable for thin structures but are more expensive to run in terms of computing power and time.

DAMAGED PLATE

The damaged plate had similar dimensions to the undamaged plate but with a central 10 mm hole. The damaged state corresponds to that where damaged material has been cut out of the plate leaving a circular hole. This represents the plate just before the repair is carried out. Damage propagation was not considered. The damaged plate was modelled to show the effect of the hole in the structure. The finite element model was constructed using the automeshing facility in NISA/DISPLAY with a stress accuracy option. The resulting mesh was thus fine enough to warrant accurate stress calculations around the hole. This area was more likely to have stress concentrations. The modelling was again straightforward.

REPAIRED PLATE

Using Siener's approach two models were constructed representing the two repair schemes: a scarf repair with a scarf angle of 3° and a stepped repair with five steps (Fig. 2a and 2b). A laminate analysis programme, LAP, was used to generate equivalent orthotropic properties for the laminate material and stacking sequence. This computer software is based on Classical Laminate Theory in which laminates are assumed to be infinite in length and width with plane stress assumed for each layer. This programme was also used to check results from the undamaged plate in tension.

For Bair's approach, only a stepped repair could be constructed (Fig. 2a). The adhesive thickness at each step was 0.1389 mm with a step length of 7.96 mm. The butt faces at each

step were 0.01 mm apart as shown on Fig. 2a. The repair length was only 39.80 mm compared to the scarf repair length of 47.70 mm.

Initially the same stepped repair used in Bair's approach was to be modelled using 3D solid elements with the same adhesive thickness but with a step length of 9.51 mm and butt faces 0.15 mm apart to be in line with practical repairs. A scarf repair model was also planned. However, for the latter, wedge shaped composite solid elements were required to represent the ideal scarf joint in Fig. 2b. As these are not available in NISA, the model was constructed with a step at each ply as shown in Fig. 2c. From this point of view, the repair modelled using 3D solid elements was closer to actual bonded repairs in its representation of the joint. As a result, the stepped repair used in Bair's approach (Fig. 2a) was not modelled.

Fig. 2: Repair schemes : (a) stepped lap joint (b) scarf joint (c) 18 step scarf joint approximation

MODELLING DATA

For all three states, the plate was loaded in tension by 10 kN with the appropriate boundary conditions to simulate a tensile test. Where appropriate, extensive use of symmetry was

made. The data in Table 1 were used for the adhesive and those in Table 2 for the carbon fibre composite.

*Table 1 Epoxy Adhesive Material Data
(Picket and Holloway)*

Young's modulus E	3000	MPa
Shear modulus, G	1103	MPa
Poisson's ratio	0.36	

Table 2 AS4/3501-6 Material Data (Source: NPL, UK)

PROPERTY(°)	Value	Unit
Young's modulus in x-direction (EX)	135584	MPa
Young's modulus in y-direction (EY)	9244	MPa
Young's modulus in z-direction (EZ*)	9244	MPa
In plane (XY) shear modulus (GXY)	5019	MPa
Out-of-plane (XZ) shear modulus (GXZ*)	5019	MPa
Out-of-plane (YZ) shear modulus (GYZ*)	5019	MPa
Poisson's ratio (NUXY)	0.3072	
Poisson's ratio (NUXZ*)	0.3072	
Poisson's ratio (NUYZ*)	0.3072	
Tensile strength in x-direction (FXT)	2178	MPa
Compressive strength in x-direction (FXC)	484	MPa
Tensile strength in y-direction (FYT)	53.4	MPa
Compressive strength in y-direction (FYC)	134	MPa
In-plane shear strength (FSXY)	34.6	MPa

* assumed

(°) nomenclature from NISA/DISPLAY

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The aim of this study was to compare these different modelling approaches. The results obtained are grouped in three main parts: displacement, adhesive tensile stress and adhesive shear stress results. These parameters provide a useful comparison of the data obtained. The main reason for the choice of these quantities as comparison parameters is the fact that in a repair joint, ultimate characteristics such as strength and efficiency, are strongly influenced by the adhesive stresses (in particular the shear stress). Thus a model's ability to evaluate these stresses is a good indication of its usefulness. Accurate displacement calculation is the first basic requirement that any finite element model must meet. A linear static analysis with a relatively low load also allows an investigation of the structural response predicted by the models.

Fig. 3(a): Longitudinal displacement (undamaged)

Fig. 3 compares the displacements along the plate centre line, predicted by the models for both undamaged and repaired states. The reference (undamaged) displacement shows good agreement between the models (Fig. 3(a)). However the mesh used for the Bair and 3D models was finer.

Fig. 3(b): Longitudinal displacement (repaired)

Fig. 3(b) also confirms that the repairs were effective as far as matching the undamaged plate displacement is concerned for both the Siener and Bair models. However, the presence of the repair patch in the 3D model is more apparent. The discontinuities in this displacement curve are located where the patch begins and ends. The curve shows the nodal displacement on the top surface of the plates and the shifts in the 3D solid curve are due to the presence of adhesive at the edge of the repair patch which is much more compliant than the adherends.

The next step is to consider adhesive tensile stress. The right hand top repair step (step 5) for the Siener and Bair models is shown in Fig. 4. The corresponding location for the 3D model are steps 13 and 14 shown in Fig. 5. The tensile stresses at these steps are plotted in Fig. 6.

Fig. 4: Top repair step location (3D model)

Fig. 5: Steps 13 and 14 (Bair and Siener models)

Fig. 6: Adhesive tensile stress

Fig. 6 indicates that there is good agreement between all three models away from step ends; the peaks observed for steps 13 and 14 of the 3D model were due to the end of the ply above each adhesive step which act as stress raiser. All three models predict high stresses at the step ends.

Fig 7: Adhesive shear stress (Stepped repair)

The final comparison parameter, the adhesive shear stress, is shown in Figs. 7 and 8 for different repair schemes using the three approaches. This stage of the comparison highlights some interesting results.

Fig. 7 shows the adhesive shear stress ratio plotted for the same steps as in Fig. 6. This ratio expresses the adhesive shear stress as a fraction of the average applied stress which is 8.37 MPa for the stepped repair used in the Bair and Siener models and 8.38 MPa for the 3D model. The values obtained from Bair's model were very small compared to Siener's and the shape of the curve was completely different from that expected. For the 3D model, the shear stress is higher with larger maximum values because the step length was shorter. However the shape of the curve is similar to Siener's model and is in accordance with previously published work [10, 11].

Fig. 8: Adhesive shear stress (Scarf repair)

When using Siener's model for the scarf repair, the shear stress was close to the average applied stress (10.05 MPa) in the central part of the adhesive (Fig. 8). One notices that in the case of the stepped repair using Siener's approach (Fig. 7), the maximum value of shear stress ratio was approximately 0.3 i.e. less than half the average applied stress. This is because in that stepped repair a large proportion of the load was transferred by the adhesive between the butt faces rather than by shear. Increasing the thickness of the adhesive between the butt faces would increase the proportion of load transferred by shear. This is apparent for the 3D model (Fig.7) which has no butt faces (Fig. 5). Given the rather small thickness of the adhesive between the butt faces in the current Bair and Siener models (0.01 mm), there are doubts on the practicality of such repair joints.

Generally, when using Siener's model, stress data for the parent laminate and the repair patch were not accurate since equivalent properties were used to generate the model. The tensile stress, for example, was uniform and approximately 160 MPa for the undamaged plate, which is inaccurate compared to the 292.7 MPa in the top layer predicted by Bair's model, 293.1 MPa by the 3D model and 292.76 MPa by the laminate analysis programme.

The results from the full 3D model were generally the most accurate. However, the solid elements used are expensive to run in terms of computing time. The same models took on average more than twice as long to run on the same machine and with the same mesh using the simplest 3D solid elements. Also, the number of composite solid element types is limited in the current version of NISA and are not available for non-linear analysis which could be a serious handicap for further study of repair joints.

CONCLUSION

This comparative study has highlighted some important features:

- Bair's model shows good agreement with traditional 2D models for direct stress calculations in the adhesive
- Bair's model gives better layer-stress results in the repair patch and parent laminates
- Bair's model produces less reliable results for adhesive shear stresses. These are best obtained using Siener's approach
- Siener's model produces poorer values for layer-stresses. This is inherent in this modelling approach
- A 3D model gives more accurate results but 3D solid elements are expensive to run

These modelling approaches should be viewed by repair engineers as complementary, providing different insights into factors affecting the adhesive and the composite structure itself; both being important for the optimisation of repair joints. This study has also shown the need for an approach which provides an overall view of bonded repairs for composite structures.

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